

EFFECT OF TILLAGE DEPTH ON TRACTOR FUEL CONSUMPTION USING OFF-SET DISC HARROW IN SANDY LOAM SOIL

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ABSTRACT

This study considered the relationship of fuel consumption and harrowing depth on sandy loam soil. A 2-wheel drive Massey Ferguson (MF) tractor coupled with off-set disc harrow was used to investigate the effect of tillage depth variation on tractor fuel consumption. Results showed that the tractor attached with disc harrow consumes 7.32, 8.60 and 9.14 liters of fuel per hectare when operated at 10, 20 and 25 cm respectively. It has also shown that a linear relationship exists between fuel consumption and depth of harrow with R² value of 0.998.

KEYWORDS: Tractor, Tillage depth, Fuel consumption, Sandy loam soil

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INTRODUCTION

Tillage is one of the most energy consuming processes in crop production. The intensity of soil tillage depends on the number of soil tillage operations, implement geometry and depth of operations (Godwin, 2007). Fuel consumption is measured by the amount of fuel used during a specific time period. The fuel consumption estimates used in fuel consumption and machinery budgets are based on the average annual fuel consumption ASAE standards, (2002). For any particular operation, the fuel consumption is determined using the equation:

$$F_c = 2.64x + 3.91 - 0.2\sqrt{738x + 173} \dots\dots\dots (ASAE, 1983)$$

Where: F_c = Fuel consumption

x = ratio of equivalent PTO power to the rated PTO power, kW.

Tillage depth is the distance from the implement's deepest penetration to the top of the soil surface. Depth of tillage has an obvious effect on the implement draft, although its relationship has only recently been investigated. Collins *et al.*, (1978) reported that tillage depth has a linear function with draft for mould board and chisel ploughs. Gunderson *et al.*, (1981) in their study on implements depth control, reported that draft has quadratic function with draft for field cultivator. There are many parameters in tillage operation that affect tractor fuel consumption. These include type and structure of soil, climate, relative humidity, tractor type (two or four wheel drive), tractor size, and the tractor-implement relationship (Fathollahzadeh *et al.*, 2000). This means that, tractor fuel consumption in different conditions is not same and varies from one situation to another.

Fuel consumption can be measured using different methods. One method is: measuring the fuel in tank before and after the test operation. But, there are many errors with this method especially when the total fuel consumption test is for short period (Fathollahzadeh *et al.*, 2009). Another method is, using flow meter sensors with high accuracy and precision on the tractor (Nielsen, 1987). In a study on a computer based instrumentation system for measuring tractor field performance, Alimardani (1987) designed a system for measuring and recording of tractors effective efficiency factor. In this study, fuel consumption of tractor was measured by two

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flow meter sensors (Model LS-4150) with appropriate measuring range between 2 – 40 liters per hour. For measuring engine fuel consumption, one sensor was placed between fuel filter and injector pump and another was placed along the passage returning fuel from injector to tank. Fuel consumption of soil tillage is correlated with intensity of soil tillage. In the energy flow from engine to implement there are efficiency losses in the engine, transmission and wheel-soil interface. Moreover slippage, which is an expression of the traction efficiency, affects the field performance and fuel consumption.

Many researches were conducted on tractor fuel consumption all over the world. These include the possibility of fuel savings and reduction of CO₂ emissions in soil tillage in Croatia by Filipovic *et al.* (2006). The fuel consumption was measured using volumetric application system. Kheiralla *et al.* (2007) also conducted a study on tractor fuel consumption at various depths and speed using oval flow meter sensor. Finally, Fathollahzadeh *et al.* (2009) conducted a research on the effect of ploughing depth on average and instantaneous tractor fuel consumption with three-share disc plough in Iran. A flow meter was used to measure the fuel consumed in this study. So far, there has been no reported study on the tractor fuel consumption in the study area. This paper, therefore, deals with influence of tillage depth on tractor fuel consumption on sandy loam soil of Borno State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Soil type

The experiment was conducted at the Department of Agricultural Engineering Research Farm, University of Maiduguri in August, 2006. The soil is a sandy loam type and consists of 77 % sand, 6 % silt, and 17 % clay which are classified as Typic Ustipsamment (Rayar, 1984). The rainy period in the area is usually between June and September, a period of about four months. This is a typical characteristic of a semi arid environment.

Tractor and Implement used in the study

A Massey Ferguson (64 kW) 2-wheel drive tractor (Model MF375E) was used in carrying out this study. An offset disc harrow (MF222) was used for harrowing during the experiment. This is because the tractor and implement are most commonly used implements for crop production in the study area. The experiment was conducted at three different tillage depths of 10, 20, and 25 cm.

Fuel Measuring System

Tractor fuel consumption was determined by refilling the fuel tank after harrowing each sub plot with the use a graduated measuring cylinder. The fuel tank was initially filled up at the beginning of operation for each sub plot. The volume of fuel used in refilling the tank gives the realistic estimate of the fuel used in harrowing the plots for every given depth under consideration.

Measurement of Soil Properties

Soil bulk density and moisture content were determined before the start of the experiment. The soil bulk density was determined using core sampler method. Three samples were collected from different locations across the field and put in plastic bags immediately so as to preserve the moisture before taking to the laboratory.

The bulk density of the soil was determined using the equation given by Yaji (2003):

$$\rho_d = \frac{\text{mass of oven dried soil}}{\text{total volume of soil}} = \frac{m}{V} = \frac{4(y-x)}{\pi d^2 h} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

- where: ρ_d = dry bulk density, g/cm³
- m = mass of dry soil, g
- V = volume of dry soil, cm³
- x = mass of can, g
- y = mass of can plus dry sample, g.

Soil samples were also taken for the determination of moisture content. The samples were weighed before and after oven drying at 105°C for 24 hours. The moisture content was determined using the equation given by Yaji (2003):

$$\omega = \frac{M_w}{M_s} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where: ω = soil moisture content, g/g
 M_w = mass of water in a soil sample, g
 M_s = mass of oven-dried soil in the sample, g

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The field trials were conducted on a plot of 2.09 ha. Sub plots measuring 30 x 30 m for each depth was replicated five times. An alley of 10 m between each plot was used to allow for free movement of the tractor during the experiment. The field was laid in a Complete Randomized Block Design. Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using regression analysis and t-test to establish the relationship between fuel consumption and tillage depth. In this study, only the tillage depth was varied, the tractor speed was maintained at the same level throughout the experiment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the average tractor fuel consumption during the study at 0.10, 0.20 and 0.25 m depth of harrowing with 5.5 % average soil moisture content and 1.424 g/cm³ bulk density. The Table showed that harrowing at 0.10, 0.20 and 0.25 m depth required 7.32, 8.60 and 9.14 liters of fuel per hectare respectively. Statistical analysis indicates significant differences (P≤0.05) between the fuel consumption values at the three different depths considered in this study (Appendix 1). As expected, the fuel consumption increased with depth of operation.

The study has also shown that a 100% increase in cutting area of soil (from 0.10 to 0.20 m depth) by harrow increases fuel consumption by 17.49%, whereas, a 25% increase (from 0.20 to 0.25 m depth) increase fuel consumption by 24.86%. The reason for more increase of fuel consumption for increasing 25% than 100% cutting area when depth changes from 0.10 to 0.25 m was due to specific draft. This result is supported by the report of Fathollahzadeh *et al.*; (2010) which said that specific draft reduces up to a certain depth, and thereafter increases.

The result also showed, (Figure 1) that, increasing the harrowing depth from 0.10 to 0.20 m (0.1 m increment) increased fuel consumption by 17.49%. Also if the depth is increased from 0.20 to 0.25 m (0.15 m increment) the fuel consumption is increased by 24.86%. Further analysis of the results showed a linear relationship (Figure 2) between fuel consumption and soil operating depth of a disc harrow and is represented by the equation below:

$$F_c = 0.12d + 6.11 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

(R² = 0.998)

where: F_c = fuel consumption, l/ha
 d = operating depth, cm

Many related studies that show the important factors affecting fuel consumption for tillage operation using different implements. Among these are: the study of Kosutic *et al.*; (2005) reported a fuel consumption value of 7.51 l/ha using disc harrow on Albic Luvisol in North-West Slovenia. Fathollahzadeh *et al.*; (2010), measured average and instantaneous fuel consumption of mouldboard plough using John Deere 3140 tractor. They reported fuel consumption values of 27.446, 30.096 and 34.060 liters of fuel hectare at depths of 0.15, 0.25 and 0.35 m respectively Kheirella *et al.*; (2007), they measured fuel consumption for a mouldboard plough with 3-shares using MF3060 tractor and reported fuel consumption values of 21.2 and 24.6 l/h for 0.18 and 0.235 m

depths respectively. Koga *et al.*; (2003) in their study, reported that a 59kW tractor operating a mouldboard plough consumed 29.8 liters of fuel per hectare. The values reported from various researches is relatively higher than in the present study. This is because they all used mouldboard plough while this study considered disc harrow.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded from this study that, tractor operating with an off-set disc harrow and operating at depths of 10, 20 and 25 cm consumes 7.32, 8.60 and 9.14 liters of fuel per hectare respectively. Increasing harrowing depth from 0.10 to 0.20 m and 0.10 to 0.25 m increase fuel consumption by 17.49 and 24.86 % respectively. The plot of fuel consumption as a function of depth gave highly correlated linear equation with R^2 value of 0.998.

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Table 1: Tractor fuel consumption for harrowing at different depths (l/ha)

Depth (cm)	Replication					Mean	standard deviation (±)
	A	B	C	D	E		
10	7.79	7.66	7.15	7.09	7.18	7.32 ^a	0.33
20	8.79	8.56	8.52	8.46	8.66	8.60 ^b	0.13
25	9.43	9.17	8.97	8.89	9.24	9.14 ^c	0.22

Figure 1: Effect of depth increment on fuel consumption

Figure 2: Fuel consumption as a function of harrowing depth

Appendix 1: Statistical analysis using regression model:

Predictor Variables	Coefficient	Std Error	T	P
Constant	6.11143	0.09583	63.77	0.0100
Depth	0.12229	0.00495	24.71	0.0257

R-Squared 0.9984

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Regression	1	1.74461	1.74461	610.61	0.0257
Residual	1	0.00286	0.00286		
Total	2	1.74747			

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